

DEVELOPMENT OF SPRING-IN ANGLE DURING CURE OF A THERMOSETTING COMPOSITE

Nuri Ersoy, Kevin Potter, and Michael R. Wisnom

*University of Bristol, Department of Aerospace Engineering
Queen's Building, University Walk
BRISTOL BS8 1TR, UNITED KINGDOM*

ABSTRACT: The development of spring-in angle during cure of AS4/8552 thermosetting composite is investigated by using a cure quench technique. The cure quench equipment consists of an aluminium tube heated by a flexible silicone heating element wrapped around the tube enabling quick release to quench the tube in water. C-shaped preforms are cured on the inner wall of the tube. A rubber diaphragm is used to transfer the pressure applied into the tube to the specimen. The cure is interrupted at various points during the Manufacturer's Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC) by quenching the tool tube into water. The diameters of the specimens cured in this way are measured and compared to the diameter of the tool tube to calculate the spring-in angle for a 90 degree arc of the specimen. The test data show that the samples quenched at earlier stages of cure exhibit a larger spring-in and the spring-in angle reduces as the specimen is further cured.

A cure kinetics simulation is performed to understand the development of cure throughout the MRCC. It has been found that the vitrification of the specimen occurs approximately 60 min after the start of the 180°C dwell period, and before that point the instantaneous glass transition temperature of the specimen is below the cure temperature. The specimens quenched before vitrification occurs are observed to have larger spring-in.

An explanation of this observation is the fact that the specimen is in the rubbery state during the temperature range between the cure temperature and the instantaneous glass temperature, and in this state it has a larger thermal expansion coefficient compared to the glassy state, causing more contraction in the transverse direction, hence more spring-in.

The cure quench experiment provides an insight into the relative importance of the thermal contraction above and below the glass transition temperature and the cure shrinkage. However, more accurate data about the instantaneous glass transition temperature during the cure cycle, and the thermal expansion coefficients above and below the glass transition temperature are needed for a more precise quantitative analysis.

KEYWORDS: Spring-in, thermoset composites, cure shrinkage, residual stress

INTRODUCTION

Composite parts with a curved geometry or a bend radius spring-in as they come out of the mould. The amount of angle closure is reported to depend on several variables: lay-up orientation, part thickness and shape, tool material and cure cycle [1-4]. Since tool correction by trial and error is an expensive and time consuming task, the development of an analytical tool to predict the spring-in taking into account various factors has also attracted a considerable research effort [5-9].

The mechanisms of spring-in can be divided in two categories: thermoelastic and non-thermoelastic components [1]. Thermoelastic spring-in refers to the shape change due to the mismatch of coefficients of thermal expansion in the in-plane and through-the-thickness directions; it is reversible when the component is heated to the process temperature. In contrast, the non-thermoelastic

component is non-reversible, and can be attributable to phenomena developing during the cure, such as cure shrinkage, consolidation, part-tool interaction, etc.

In this study a methodology is developed to further the understanding of how the geometry develops during the cure process and what the relative contributions of the thermoelastic and non thermoelastic components are. The intermittent technique, first proposed by White and Hahn [10] is adopted and modified to a cure quench technique, in which the composite part curing on the inner wall of an aluminium tube is quenched into water to obtain very high cooling rates. The experimental data is interpreted in terms of the various components of spring-in and reveals important information about the relative contributions of each component to the final spring-in angle.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cure Quench Equipment

The cure quench equipment shown in Fig.1 consists of an aluminium tube with 63 mm inner diameter, 70 mm outer diameter and 300 mm length. A hole has been drilled in the tube to allow application of vacuum and venting. Heat is applied with the help of a flexible silicone heating element wrapped around the tube (Fig.1.a). The heating element is fitted with boot hooks enabling quick release. After removing the heating element, the tube can be quenched in water. Fig. 1.b shows the lay-up for curing the samples. The prepreg is wrapped around $\frac{3}{4}$ of the perimeter of a tube of comparable diameter to make a 8-ply C-shaped preform of 270 degrees. All samples are of $[90]_8$ layup with the fibers running in the hoop direction. Layers of PTFE coated glass fabric release film were used between the aluminium tube and composite as well as the composite and breather cloth. A silicone rubber diaphragm was used to transfer the pressure applied in the tube to the composite.

The temperature is controlled with a programmable PID process controller within a $\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ band around the process temperature. The uniformity of the temperature is checked with eight thermocouples around the outer surface of the tube. The MRCC consists of a first ramp of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 120°C and a first hold at 120°C for 60 min, a second ramp of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 180°C and a second hold at 180°C for 120 min. A pressure of 0.7 MPa is applied throughout the cycle. The quench rate attained during the experiments is $600^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

The outer diameter of the composite parts are measured at room temperature and spring-in angles are calculated for a 90° angle with respect to the tube inner diameter measured at 180°C using a ball nose gauge.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spring-In Angles

The spring-in angles of the samples are listed in Table 1 together with the respective times when they are quenched. If they are plotted against time together with the MRCC (Fig.2), a rather peculiar phenomenon is observed. The spring-in angles of the specimens quenched at the early stages of cure development are first increasing as the cure develops in the first ramp, and then decreasing in the later stages of the cure, forming a “peak-and-decay” behaviour.

Fig.1 Cure quench experiment setup (a) The quenchable aluminium tube with flexible silicone heater (b) the lay-up of the samples

Table 1. Dimensional measurements of the samples.

Sample #		5	14	6	8	13	12	10	4	3	9
Quench Time	min	130	135	140	140	150	160	200	200	250	260
Spring-in	degrees	0.94	1.07	1.36	1.38	1.31	1.20	1.11	1.18	1.08	1.08

Fig. 2 Spring-in values of quenched samples

Cure Kinetics

In order to gain further understanding of the test results obtained from the interrupted cure experiments, the development of cure during the manufacturing cycle is modelled using the cure

kinetics model proposed by Cole et al. [11], which takes into account a shift from kinetics to diffusion control:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \frac{Ka^m(1-a)^n}{1 + e^{C[a-(a_{c0}+a_{CT}T)]}} \quad (1)$$

where $K = Ae^{(-\Delta E/RT)}$, ΔE is the activation energy, A is the pre-exponential cure rate coefficient, m and n are first and second exponential constants, C is the diffusion constants, a_{c0} is the critical degree of cure at $T=0$ K, and a_{CT} is the constant accounting for the increase in critical resin degree of cure with temperature. However the constants of the model are recalculated by using dynamic DSC tests performed in a TA Instruments DSC 2920 Modulated DSC at QinetiQ, UK [12]. The MRCC is simulated in DSC for both prepreg and the neat resin, and no difference is found between the two. The values of the constants are given in Appendix A

Resin samples squeezed out of cure quenched samples during processing are also tested by DSC for residual heat of reaction and glass transition temperature, T_g . The tests are performed at a rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ until the temperature reaches 300°C . The degree of cure of these samples can be found from the residual heat of reaction, H_R and ultimate heat of reaction, H_U (which is measured to be 574 ± 13 J/g) using the formula:

$$a = 1 - \frac{H_R}{H_U} \quad (2)$$

In Fig. 3 T_g is plotted versus a and a best line is fitted to the experimental data, which gives the relationship between T_g and a as:

$$T_g = -78 + 286a \quad (3)$$

where T_g is in Celsius.

Fig. 3 Glass transition temperature plotted against the degree of cure for 8552 neat resin.

In Fig. 4, the process temperature, T , the glass transition temperature, T_g , calculated using Eq. 1, and a predicted by the cure kinetics model are plotted versus time throughout the MRCC, together with the DSC measurements of a and T_g for cure quenched samples. Initial degree of cure is assumed to be zero. There is excellent agreement between the model predictions and the experimental measurements. From the graph it can be seen that vitrification occurs approximately 60 minutes after the 180°C soak period starts. It should be noted that vitrification is the change of state of the polymer from a rubbery, viscoelastic solid to a glassy, elastic solid. At the vitrification point, the instantaneous

glass transition temperature of the resin, which is increasing throughout the process due to the increasing cross-linking density, reaches the process temperature.

Fig 4. Cure kinetics model predictions for degree of cure plotted versus time throughout the MRCC. The degree of cure and T_g measurements of quenched samples are superimposed. The T_g line corresponds to the linear fit between a and T_g

In a separate test to find the gel point of the curing resin, two layers of prepreg were pulled out from between another two layers, which they were cured between two heating plates replicating the MRCC. The gel point of the resin exhibits itself as a sharp rise in the force required and is measured to be at around 165°C during the second ramp, and this corresponds to a degree of cure of $a=0.40$. The gel point is defined as the state where enough polymer chains are bonded together (either physically or chemically) such that at least one very large molecule is formed.

Explanation of the the “peak-and-decay” behaviour

The “peak-and-decay” behaviour that the quenched samples exhibit is not in accord with the results obtained in previous research on curvature development in [0/90] strips during the cure cycle which shows that the curvature increases up to the point of vitrification and then remains constant [13].

An explanation of this observation is the fact that the specimen is in the rubbery state through the temperature range between the process temperature and the instantaneous glass transition temperature. A similar mechanism was proposed by Svanberg and Holmberg [14] to explain the spring-out phenomena in postcuring of partially cured corner sections. If the resin is not vitrified at the point where the specimen is quenched, it may be assumed that in the temperature range from the process temperature, T_p , to the glass temperature, T_g (i.e., $T_p > T > T_g$) the specimen has a larger coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) compared to the glassy state, causing more contraction in the transverse direction, hence more spring-in. A schematic explanation of that phenomenon is given in Fig. 5.

When the specimen starts to cure, a certain amount of non-thermoelastic spring-in may be developed due to both cure shrinkage and part-tool interaction (point A in Fig. 5). However, for the time being, the part-tool interaction is assumed negligible, and all non-thermoelastic spring-in is assumed to be attributable to only cure shrinkage. If the specimen is fully vitrified, it will be in the glassy state with an equilibrium glass transition temperature $T_{g,\infty}$, and it will cool down following the path A-B. However if the specimen is not vitrified at the processing temperature T_p , the glass transition temperature T_{g2} is below T_p , and it will cool down from T_p in the rubbery state up to T_{g2} (path A-C), and from that point onwards it will cool down in glassy state (path C-D). If the degree of cure is

less, then T_g will be lower, and the specimen will cool down following the path A-E-F, resulting in more spring-in. So partially cured specimens will have a higher degree of spring-in compared to the fully cured specimens.

Fig 6. Spring-in above and below the glass transition temperature

In order to explain this phenomenon better, a qualitative analysis is performed by neglecting the tool-part interaction and consolidation as contributors to the final spring-in, and the analysis is kept simple to understand the basic mechanisms of geometry development during the cure process and the relative contributions of the thermoelastic and cure shrinkage components.

The conventional formula [1] to predict the spring-in is modified to take into account the component of spring-in taking place above T_g :

$$\Delta\theta = \theta \left\{ \left[\frac{(\alpha_L^{T > T_g} - \alpha_T^{T > T_g})(T_p - T_g)}{1 - \alpha_T^{T > T_g} \Delta T} \right] + \left[\frac{(\alpha_L^{T < T_g} - \alpha_T^{T < T_g})(T_g - T_{RT})}{1 - \alpha_T^{T < T_g} \Delta T} \right] + \left[\frac{\varepsilon_L^c - \varepsilon_T^c}{1 - \varepsilon_T^c} \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

where the first and second terms on the right hand side of the equation give the spring-in due to the thermal contraction above and below the glass transition temperature respectively, and the third term is due to chemical shrinkage. T_p is the temperature at which the specimen is quenched, T_{RT} is the room temperature, $\alpha_L^{T > T_g}$ and $\alpha_T^{T > T_g}$ are the in-plane and the through-thickness CTEs above T_g respectively, whereas $\alpha_L^{T < T_g}$ and $\alpha_T^{T < T_g}$ are their counterpart below T_g , and ε_L^c and ε_T^c are the in-plane and through-thickness chemical strains. For practical reasons the in-plane CTEs and in-plane chemical strains are assumed to be zero due to the high stiffness of the fibres in the fibre direction.

CTEs of the composite are found from resin coefficients of thermal expansion using the micromechanics formula [16]:

$$\alpha_T = (\alpha_T^f + \nu_1^f)V_f + (\alpha^r + \nu^r \alpha^r)(1 - V_f) \quad (5)$$

where α^r is the resin CTE and ν^r is the resin poisson ratio, α_T^f is the CTE of carbon fibers in the transverse direction, and V_f is the fiber volume fraction. The values for resin CTEs above and below T_g given in Appendix A are found by group interaction modelling of the monomers and the cured

polymer done at QinetiQ, UK [15], and are only estimates in the absence of experimental data. The value for α_{Tf} is taken from Bogetti and Gillespie [16].

The cure shrinkage strains are calculated as follows: The resin volumetric cure shrinkage strain is given to be $V_{rco}=0.099$ by Johnson [8]. He proposes that the cure shrinkage takes place between $a=0.055$ and $a=0.651$, and further curing of the resin does not cause shrinkage. In this study a linear relationship between degree of cure and volumetric strain is assumed over this range. However the shrinkage below the gelpoint, $a=0.40$ should not contribute to spring-in, since the resin is in a viscous state before that point.

If the resin shrinkage strains are assumed to be completely constrained in the fiber direction, the composite shrinkage strains in the transverse and thickness directions are given as [8]:

$$\varepsilon_r^c = \left(\sqrt[3]{V_r^c + 1} - 1 \right) (1 - V_f) (1 + \nu_f) \quad (6)$$

where V_r^c is the volumetric shrinkage strain, and V_f is the fiber volume fraction, and ν_f is the Poisson's ratio of the resin, the values of which are given in Appendix A.

In Fig. 6 the development of the components of spring-in are plotted with the instantaneous T_g throughout the MRCC. The vitrification point of the resin is at around 60 min. in the second hold. During the early stage of cure in the second ramp in MRCC, the process temperature increases faster than T_g , and the temperature range over which the specimen cools down in the rubbery state is increasing, together with the component of the spring-in at rubbery state, $\Delta\theta^{T>T_g}$, calculated using rubbery CTE, $\alpha_T^{T>T_g}$ and the temperature difference between the process temperature and the T_g (first term in Eq. 4). After the temperature drops down to the instantaneous T_g during quenching, the resin passes from the rubbery to glassy state, and the samples keep on cooling in the glassy state with a smaller CTE, $\alpha_T^{T<T_g}$. The component of spring-in taking place in the glassy state, $\Delta\theta^{T<T_g}$ is calculated using the glassy CTE, $\alpha_T^{T<T_g}$ and the temperature difference between the instantaneous T_g and the room temperature.

The difference between the total spring-in and the thermoelastic spring-in gives the non-thermoelastic component of the spring-in, which is assumed to be due to cure shrinkage only, neglecting the part-tool interaction effects. The component of the spring-in attributable to the cure shrinkage, i.e. $\Delta\theta^{cure}$, is also plotted in Fig. 6.

If the three components, i.e., $\Delta\theta^{T<T_g}$, $\Delta\theta^{T>T_g}$, and $\Delta\theta^{cure}$ are added we find the total spring-in, which matches the experimental data fairly well.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The cure quench experiments provide an insight into the relative importance of the thermal contraction above and below the glass transition temperature and the cure shrinkage. The higher values of spring-in in partially cured samples are explained by the higher values of coefficient of thermal expansion above the glass transition temperature of the resin. The thermoelastic component accounts for only 50% of the final spring-in in fully cured components. However, more accurate experimental data about the thermal expansion coefficients above and below the glass transition temperature as well as cure shrinkage are needed for a more precise quantitative analysis. The locked-in stresses due to part-tool interaction and the stresses developed in the reinforcement due to constraints on slip during consolidation should also be investigated using experimental techniques such as slitting or ply removal.

Fig. 10. Components contributing to the final spring-in

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors want to thank to QinetiQ, Farnborough, UK for developing the cure kinetics model and the CTEs of the resin above and below the glass transition temperatures based on group interaction modelling. The work reported here is a part of ongoing programme supported by QinetiQ, Airbus UK, Agusta Westland, and the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council of UK.

REFERENCES

- [1] Radford, D.W. and Rennick, T.S. Separating Sources of Manufacturing Distortion in Laminated Composites, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 2000;19(8):621–641.
- [2] Albert C. and Fernlund G. Spring-in and warpage of angled composite laminates, *Composites Science and Technology* 2002;62: 1895–1912.
- [3] Fernlund, G., Rahman, N., Courdji, R., Bresslauer, M., Poursartip, A., Willden, K., Nelson, K. Experimental and numerical study of the effect of cure cycle, tool surface, geometry, and lay-up on the dimensional fidelity of autoclave-processed composite parts. *Composites: Part A* 2002;33:341-351.
- [4] Darrow, D.A.Jr. and Smith, L.W. Isolating components of processing induced warpage in laminated composites. *Journal of Composite Materials* 2002;36(21): 2407-2419.
- [5] Wiersma, H.W., Peeters, L.J.B., and Akkerman, R. Prediction of springforward in continuous-fiber/polymer L-shaped parts. *Composites Part A* 1998;29A: 1333-1242.

- [6] Wang, J., Kelly D., and Hillier, W. Finite element analysis of temperature induced stresses and deformations of polymer composite components. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2000;34(17): 1456-1471.
- [7] Zhu, Q., Geubelle, P. H., Li, M. Tucker C. L. III, Dimensional Accuracy of Thermoset Composites: Simulation of Process-Induced Residual Stresses, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2001;35(24): 2171-2205.
- [8] Johnston, A. An integrated model of the development of process-induced deformation in autoclave processing of composites structures, Ph.D. thesis, The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, 1997.
- [9] Johnston, A. Vaziri, R., and Poursartip, A. A plane strain model for process-induced deformation of laminated composite structures, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2001;35(16): 1435-1469.
- [10] White, S. R. and Hahn H.T. Process modelling of composite materials: Residual stress development during cure. Part II. Experimental validation. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1992;26(16): 2423-2453.
- [11] K.C. Cole, J.J. Hechler, and D. Noël, "A New Approach to Modeling the Cure Kinetics of Epoxy Amine Thermosetting Resin. 2. Application to a Typical System Based on Bis[4-diglycidylamino]phenyl]methane and Bis(4-aminophenyl) Sulphone", *Macromolecules* 1991;24 (11):3098-3110.
- [12] Clegg, M. from QinetiQ, UK, personal communication.
- [13] Gigliotti, M., Wisnom, M.R., and Potter, K.D. Development of curvature during the cure of AS4/8552 [0/90] unsymmetric composite plates. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2003;63(2):187-197.
- [14] Svanberg, J.M. and Holmberg J.A., An experimental investigation on mechanisms for manufacturing induced shape distortions in homogeneous and balanced laminates. *Composites: Part A* 2001;32:827-838.
- [15] Porter, D., QinetiQ, UK, personal communication.
- [16] Bogetti, T.A. and Gillespie Jr. J. W. Process-induced stress and deformation in thick-section thermoset composite laminates. *Journal of Composite Materials* 1992;26(5): 626-660.

APPENDIX A-MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Cure Kintetics		Unit	Comments
E_a	65000	J/gmol	Activation energy
A	7.00E+04	s^{-1}	Cure rate coefficient
m	0.5		First exponential constant
n	1.5		Second exponential constant
R	8.314	J/mol/K	Gas constant
C	30		Diffusion constant
a_{CT}	0		Critical degree of cure at T=0K
a_{CO}	0.85		Costant accounting for increase in ultimate α with T
a_{gel}	0.40		Degree of cure at gel point
Resin properties			
ν^r	0.37		Resin Poison's ratio
$\alpha^{r,T < T_g}$	6.07E-05	$^{\circ}C^{-1}$	Resin CTE below T_g
$\alpha^{r,T > T_g}$	1.24E-04	$^{\circ}C^{-1}$	Resin CTE above T_g
Fiber properties			
ν_{12}	0.2		Fiber Poison's ratio
α_T^f	7.20E-06	$^{\circ}C^{-1}$	Fiber CTE in transverse direction
V_f	0.60		Fiber volume fraction
Composite properties			
$\alpha_T^{T < T_g}$	3.75E-05	$^{\circ}C^{-1}$	Composite transverse CTE below T_g
$\alpha_T^{T > T_g}$	7.19E-05	$^{\circ}C^{-1}$	Composite transverse CTE above T_g